

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES AND THE FIBRE/MATRIX INTERFACE IN
SQUEEZE-CAST GRAPHITE-MAGNESIUM
METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Squeeze-cast samples of Gr/Mg and Gr/Mg-Al MMC's have been tensile tested in the as-cast condition and after heat treatment. Tests were carried out at room temperature, 200°C and 350°C. The mechanical properties were apparently improved by increases in test temperature and the macroscopic fracture morphology changed very noticeably from flat to extremely rough corresponding to a much greater degree of fibre bundle pull-out. Samples were examined in the transmission electron microscope so as to characterise the fibre/matrix interface. It was found that there was little evidence of reaction between fibre and matrix, even after heat treatment. Nevertheless, the interface exhibited characteristic needle-like features which are, as yet, unidentified but which are probably a carbide phase.

INTRODUCTION

Graphite fibre reinforced magnesium metal matrix composites (Gr/Mg MMC's) are an attractive class of materials for automotive, aerospace and other structural applications because of their high specific strength and stiffness, low coefficients of thermal expansion and resistance to moisture [1-2]. Rawal et al. [3] recently reported a microstructural study of diffusion bonded and investment cast Gr/Mg AZ91C, this matrix alloy being a common casting alloy. No interfacial reaction was found to occur and the interface integrity was stated to be good.

Successful development and application of any new material demands a thorough understanding of the processing-structure-property relationships and whilst Gr/Al MMC's have been extensively investigated, there is little comparable data concerning Gr/Mg MMC's. The results reported here are the initial results of a systematic study of a simple Gr/Mg MMC system aimed at

the structure/property relationships.

EXPERIMENTAL

The matrices used in this work were commercially pure magnesium (c.p. Mg), Mg-2wt%Al and Mg-4wt%Al: the matrices were unidirectionally reinforced with 30vol% of T300 PAN-based high tensile fibres. The squeeze castings were produced by Honda R. & D. Co. Ltd., Wako-shi, Japan. Testing was carried out upon samples in the as-cast condition as well as upon some in the T4 condition; this heat treated condition corresponds to a treatment of 24 hrs. at 400°C followed by a hot water quench and is a typical commercial heat treatment for magnesium alloys.

Cylindrical tensile specimens with a gauge length of 25.4mm and diameter of 5mm were machined from the squeeze castings and tested in air on a screw driven Instron machine at an initial strain rate of either 5×10^{-2} or $8 \times 10^{-3} \text{min}^{-1}$. Stress vs. strain and Young's Modulus data were collected for each specimen by means of strain gauges attached to the gauge length. The temperature of the specimens tested at high temperature was monitored by two thermocouples in contact with opposite ends of the gauge section. The total heating-up and temperature equilibration time for these tests was less than one hour.

After testing, the fracture surfaces were examined in the scanning electron microscope (SEM) and slices were also cut from the grip section for optical microscopy and for preparation of transmission electron microscope (TEM) samples. 3mm diameter discs were cut perpendicular to the tensile axis for TEM so as to facilitate observation and interpretation of the fibre/matrix interface structure. The discs were mechanically ground to <70µm thick and then ion milled to electron transparency at 3.5keV. All samples were examined in a Philips EM400T at 100keV.

RESULTS

The results of tensile tests performed on the as-cast MMC's are presented in Table 1 and show that the mechanical properties are improved significantly by the addition of 2% aluminium to the magnesium matrix. However, it can be seen that, whilst the addition of 2% aluminium is very beneficial, little advantage is gained by further increasing this addition to 4%.

Tensile data for the T4 heat treated Mg-4Al samples are shown in Table 2 and the room temperature properties of the MMC are seen, by comparison with Table 1, to be almost unaffected by the heat treatment apart from a slight decrease in Young's Modulus. However, the total elongation to fracture is considerably reduced. At 350°C the increases in strength and Young's Modulus were more modest and the elongation remained at its room temperature value.

Sections prepared for optical microscopy showed that in the as-cast material the macrostructure changed from a coarse grained, heavily twinned, single phase matrix, Fig. 1(a), to a pronounced dendritic structure as the aluminium content increased to 4%. Figure 1(b) shows a region between fibre tows in which the dark interdendritic areas are the intermetallic phase corresponding to the last portion of the melt to solidify during the squeeze-casting process. These optical macrostructures were essentially

unaffected by the heat treatment applied and by the exposure to high temperature which occurred during elevated temperature tensile testing.

TABLE 1
Room temperature test data for as-cast composites

	c.p. Mg	Matrix Mg-2Al	Mg-4Al
Tensile strength MPa	522	655	645
Young's Modulus GPa	84	88.7	92.5
Elongation %	0.61	0.75	0.76

TABLE 2
Tensile test data for T4 heat treated Mg-4Al MMC's

	RT	Test temperature	
		200°C	350°C
Tensile strength MPa	629	759	694
Young's Modulus GPa	85.0	108.9	97.9
Elongation %	0.72	0.66	0.71

The fracture surfaces of as-cast c.p. Mg and Mg-2Al MMC's were macroscopically rough, with typical height variations of ~ 5 mm across the surface. In general, individual fibre tows had fractured at different regions along the tensile axis and the subsequent joining up of these regions by failure of the inter-tow boundaries produced the macroscopic roughness. On a fibre scale, the fracture surface appearance was dependent upon local fibre volume fraction and where this was high, in the centre of individual tows, the surface was flat with almost no fibre pull-out, Fig. 2(a). Where the fibre volume fraction was locally lower, e.g. at the tow boundaries, considerable matrix ductility was noted and the fibres were debonded and located in individual ductile dimples, Fig. 2(b). In the as-cast Mg-4Al MMC's, the macroscopic fracture surface appearance was much smoother, typically ~ 3 mm height differences, but fibre pull-out was much more noticeable, Fig. 3(a). No reaction products or general precipitation could be found by SEM at the fibre/matrix interface although the surface roughness of the fibres was very clearly shown, Fig. 3(b).

After T4 heat treatment, the room temperature fracture surface of the Mg-4Al MMC resembled that of the as-cast Mg-4Al MMC. However, the surface became progressively rougher as the test temperature increased, Fig. 4(a)

Figure 1; (a) As-cast Gr/c.p. Mg MMC showing heavily twinned matrix between tows. (b) As-cast Gr/Mg-2Al MMC showing interdendritic phase in tow boundaries

Figure 2; (a) Gr/c.p. Mg MMC showing flat tow failure with little fibre pull-out. (b) Gr/c.p. Mg MMC showing failure at tow boundary, low V_f , and essentially ductile matrix failure.

until at 350°C massive amounts of matrix shear had occurred, Fig. 4(b).

Figure 3; (a) Gr-Mg-4Al MMC showing extensive fibre pull-out. (b) Rough fibre surfaces with no evidence of reaction products.

Figure 4, T4 heat treated Gr/Mg-4Al: (a) tested at 200°C showing extensive shear within the tows, (b) tested at 350°C showing massive shear within the tows.

Selected samples were next examined by TEM. In general, three distinct types of interfacial structure were found in these MMC's and each structure was found to some extent in each sample examined although the relative amounts of each structure varied somewhat from sample to sample. The most common type of structure was as shown in Fig. 5 and consisted of an essentially featureless interface in which the matrix was in intimate contact with the fibre and there was no evidence of any type of chemical reaction. This type of interface was most common in the c.p. Mg matrix MMC and appeared to comprise >95% of the total fibre/matrix interface area.

Figure 5: As-cast Gr/c.p. Mg MMC, fibre/matrix interface showing intimate contact and no evidence of reaction, (TEM micrograph).

The next type of structure was one in which a thin amorphous layer separated the fibre and matrix. This layer was firmly attached to the matrix, into which it appeared to be growing, and yielded a very diffuse amorphous ring in electron diffraction. When dark field images were formed from the ring, the layer showed bright regions on a 1-3nm scale indicating very fine crystallinity, Fig. 6 (a) & (b). Energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) with a Be window detector revealed nothing other than Mg and Al in this layer, however, C and O are not detectable with such a detector.

The final common type of structure at the interface was one in which there was again intimate fibre/matrix contact but numerous long slender needles protruded from the interface into the matrix, Fig. 7. These features are probably, in fact, sheets ~ 0.1 nm thick which become visible when they lie nearly parallel to the electron beam. It was frequently noted that these features appear to have a preferred crystallographic orientation but no habit plane has yet been determined. Again, EDS did

Figure 6, As-cast Gr/c.p. Mg MMC showing 'amorphous' layer at fibre/matrix interface: (a) bright field TEM micrograph, (b) dark field micrograph taken with part of the ring diffraction pattern showing fine scale crystallinity.

Figure 7, Interfacial needle-like particles (arrowed) in Gr/Mg-4Al MMC.

not reveal any significant compositional variations within these regions. This type of interfacial appearance was seen in samples containing Al in the matrix and whilst these needles have not yet been identified it is presently assumed that they represent an aluminium or aluminium/magnesium carbide. The rather irregular, crooked appearance of these features may be due to shears arising due to differences in thermal contraction between the fibres and matrix on cooling.

In addition to the general interfacial structures noted above, it was found that, as the matrix Al content increased, progressively more particles were observed at the interface. These particles were typically $\sim 0.1\mu\text{m}$ in size and EDS showed them to be an Mg/Al compound with a composition approximating to $\text{Mg}_{17}\text{Al}_{12}$. These particles are not reaction products, rather they are due to normal precipitation processes which occur during cooling Mg-Al alloys. Two such particles are visible in Figure 7 in addition to the slender needles mentioned above.

Figure 8 shows the typical appearance of a Gr/Mg-4Al sample in the T4 condition in which all of the features noted above can be seen. Neither the heat treatment nor the thermal exposure accompanying testing caused any differences in the interfacial structure.

Figure 8, T4 heat treated Gr/Mg-4Al MMC showing needle-like particles, small equiaxed particles and amorphous layer at interfaces between matrix and two fibres.

DISCUSSION

The above results show a clear increase in strength as small amounts of Al are added to the matrix and as the test temperature is increased. In as-cast MMC's the strength increase is associated with a change in fracture morphology. The c.p. Mg MMC's failed by the fracture of whole tows at different places along the gauge length: link up of these regions by subsequent matrix failure led to a highly serrated fracture surface consisting of many cliffs and plateaus. This type of fracture surface is typical of composite systems in which there is a strong fibre/matrix bond. Further supporting evidence for this view is found in the TEM micrograph showing excellent fibre/matrix contact with no reaction, see Fig. 5.

Hardness measurements showed that the addition of 4% Al caused a ~50% increase in the matrix hardness as a result of grain size and solid solution strengthening and this alone is sufficient to cause an ~80MPa increase in tensile strength in this composite which only exhibits half of the R.O.M. strength. Thus, much of the strength increase noted with increasing aluminium content may be attributed directly to the stronger matrix. However, the increased amount of fibre pull-out, Fig. 3, indicates that the fibre/matrix interfacial shear strength is also decreasing. TEM observations again provide supporting evidence for this contention since needle like (carbide) particles and other Mg/Al intermetallic phases have been found at the interface, Figs. 7 & 8. According to the model of Shorshorov et al. [4] a decrease in interfacial shear strength leads to an increase in composite strength and the composite exhibits a so-called cumulative mode of fracture in which fibre pull-out is the dominant failure mode.

Considering the T4 heat treated MMC's, the room temperature properties, hardness, microstructure and fracture surfaces are the same as those of as-cast MMC's. It is clear, therefore, that this particular heat treatment has no discernible effect upon properties. As the test temperature is increased to 350°C the tensile strengths of typical Mg casting alloys decrease by a factor of ~4 [5] and hence the matrix shear strength will decrease similarly. The fractographic observations are, again, in accord with the trends predicted by the model of Shorshorov et al. [4] in terms of cumulative and non-cumulative failure. Furthermore, their model also predicts that, in the cumulative mode, fibres break at a maximum stress as given by the Weibull distribution function and this is reflected in the higher strengths measured at higher temperature.

Whilst the overall trends in strength levels can be explained on the basis of the above arguments it is obvious that the optimum strengths are not currently obtained in these MMC's since they exhibit strengths of less than half the R.O.M. values. Recent work by Ochiai and co-workers [6] has demonstrated that similar great changes in mechanical properties occur in the Gr/Al system when the condition of the interface is altered by surface coating the fibres. Further work is aimed at a more quantitative treatment of the strengthening mechanisms and fracture processes and a more complete characterization of the fibre/matrix interface.

Additional work is also under way to study the corrosion problems in these MMC's since it is believed to be possible that the 'amorphous' layer shown in Figs. 6 represents the early stages of corrosion in spite of the care taken in specimen preparation, transfer and storage. The appearance of carbides at the fibre/matrix interface would render it a prime location for incipient corrosion as occurs in Gr/Al MMC's.

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